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EFFECTIVENESS OF POSTOPERATIVE INTENSIVE THERAPY IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH VARICOSE VEINS.....12

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DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF INFLAMMATORY PROCESSES IN DIFFERENTIATING PARKINSONISM SUBTYPES.....18
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EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENTAL DISORDERS IN CHILDREN BORN FROM CONSANGUINEOUS MARRIAGES.....26
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CORRECTION OF DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS AND EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COMPREHENSIVE REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH CHEMICAL ADDICTIVE DISORDERS.....34
5. **Turaev Bobir Temirpulotovich, Sultanov Shoxrux Khabibullaevich**
FACTORS INFLUENCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MEDICAL AND SOCIAL REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH CHEMICAL ADDICTIVE DISORDERS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....41
6. **Khakimova Sakhiba Ziyadulloevna, Gaffarova Parvina Abdurafikovna**
ETIOPATHOGENETIC SIGNIFICANCE OF MAO-B INHIBITORS IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE AND THEIR ROLE IN REDUCING MOTOR SYMPTOMS.....48
7. **Mirzhuraev Elbek Mirshavkatovich, Adambaev Zufar Ibragimovich, Mamatkhanova Charos Bahodirovna**
STRATIFICATION OF MANAGEMENT FOR PATIENTS WITH COMBINED VERTEBROGENIC PATHOLOGY AND PELVIC ORGAN DYSFUNCTION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACH.....55
8. **Rogov Alexey Vladimirovich, Lipartiya Mary Givievna**
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SEVERITY OF PARANOID SCHIZOPHRENIA IN PATIENTS WITH AUTOAGGRESSIVE MANIFESTATIONS IN THE EARLY PERIOD OF THE DISEASE.....63

MORPHOLOGY

9. **Kiyomov Ikhtiyor Ergashevich, Islamov Shavkat Erjigitovich**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE THYMUS DURING ACUTE EXPOSURE TO A DEFOLIANT.....69

ONCOLOGY

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HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS AND OROPHARYNGEAL CANCER: CURRENT CLINICAL-EPIDEMIOLOGICAL AND PROGNOSTIC ASPECTS (REVIEW).....77

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STUDY OF THE DYNAMICS OF PROLACTIN AND GLUCOSE LEVELS IN PATIENTS WITH GASTRIC CANCER DURING THE PERIOPERATIVE PERIOD UNDER COMBINED EPIDURAL ANESTHESIA.....89
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EVALUATION OF RADIATION DOSE LOAD TO ORGANS AT RISK WHEN SWITCHING TO A HYPOFRACTIONATED REGIMEN OF POSTOPERATIVE RADIOTHERAPY FOR LEFT BREAST CANCER.....95
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ACOUSTIC ANALYSIS OF VOICE FUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH BENIGN LARYNGEAL LESIONS.....101
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OUR EXPERIENCE OF PERCUTANEOUS BIOPSY IN METASTATIC LESIONS OF THE LUMBAR SPINE.....105
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ISOLATED LATERAL SURGICAL APPROACH FOR VERTEBRAL BODY TUMORS WITH EXTRADURAL INTRACANAL INVASION AT TH11–L2.....109
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POSTERIOR DECOMPRESSIVE AND STABILIZING APPROACH FOR THORACIC AND LUMBAR VERTEBRAL BODY TUMORS WITH INTRACANAL EXTENSION.116
17. **Umarov Rustam Dilshodovich, Alimov Ijod Rustamovich, Ten Vladimir Denisovich**
ISOLATED LATERAL SURGICAL APPROACH FOR VERTEBRAL BODY TUMORS WITH EXTRADURAL INTRACANAL INVASION AT TH11–L2 LEVELS.....121
18. **Sharopov Sadullo Shukurillovich**
CORRELATION BETWEEN ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAPHIC CHANGES AND MRI CHARACTERISTICS IN PATIENTS WITH BRAIN TUMORS.....129

MEDICAL REHABILITATION

19. **Raimkulova Dilnoza Farkhaddinovna**
PROGNOSTIC CRITERIA AND ANALYSIS OF PHYSICAL PERFORMANCE IN ADOLESCENTS ENGAGED IN DIFFERENT TYPES OF SPORTS.....135
20. **Mamatkhanova Charos Bahodirovna**
STRATIFICATION OF SURGICAL AND REHABILITATION TREATMENT FOR POST-TRAUMATIC MYELOPATHIES AT THE CERVICAL AND THORACIC SPINE LEVELS.....142
21. **Mamatkhanova Charos Bahodirovna**
ANALYSIS OF PATIENTS WITH SPINAL PATHOLOGY AND SPINAL CORD DISEASES AT THE REPUBLICAN CENTER FOR REHABILITATION OF DISABLED PERSONS.....149
22. **Tukhtaev Firdavs Mukhitdinovich, Kadirov Jonibek Fayzullayevich**
THE IMPACT OF MINERAL AND ACID–BASE METABOLIC CORRECTION ON POSTOPERATIVE REHABILITATION IN CHILDREN WITH UROLITHIASIS.....155

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

23. **Boymurodov Shukhrat Abdujalilovich, Kurbanov Yoqubjon Khamdamovich, Yusupov Shokhrukh Shuhratovich, Djurayev Jamolbek Abdukakharovich, Soatov Ilyosjon Olimovich**
SIGNIFICANCE OF IL10 RS1800872, SERPINE1 RS1799768, NOS3 RS2070744, AND IL1B RS1143627 GENE POLYMORPHISMS IN PURULENT-NECROTIC PROCESSES OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION.....160

24. **Alyavi Mufassal Nasirkhanovna, Khaydarov Artur Mikhaylovich, Alieva Muattar Abdulkhayevna**
COMPLEX TREATMENT OF CHRONIC GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS IN PATIENTS WITH STABLE ANGINA PECTORIS.....171
25. **Ismoilov Mirkamol Xusan o'g'li Nigmatova Iroda Maratovna**
THE ROLE OF VITAMIN D IN THE CONDITION OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES DURING ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT IN PREGNANT WOMEN.....180
26. **Irgashev Shokhrukh Khasanovich**
ANALYSIS OF THE HYGIENIC INDICATORS OF THE ORAL MUCOSA OF PERSONS WHO HAVE UNDERGONE ORTHOPEDIC STOMATOLOGICAL TREATMENT.....190
27. **Ibragimova Malika Khudaiberganovna, Abduvahobova Dilnoza Anvarovna**
CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC ASPECTS OF RED FLAT AND DEPRESSED ORAL MUCOSA.....196
28. **Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich, Akhmedova Sayyora Mukhamadovna, Absalamova Nigora Fakhriddinovna**
IMPROVEMENT OF TREATMENT STRATEGIES FOR ORAL MUCOSAL LEUKOPLAKIA BASED ON IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL RESULTS.....204
29. **Otkhonova Mohinog Ganiyon qizi, Khramova Natalya Vladimirovna, Gafurov Zafar Atkhamovich**
JUSTIFICATION OF MAXILLARY RECONSTRUCTION USING A TIBIAL BONE AUTOGRAFT.....212
30. **Madazimov Madamin Muminovich, Turaev Feruz Fakhtullaevich, Yusufovna Mohamed Khava, Pustovetova Maria Gennadievna, Akramova Nozima Akramovna**
CELL-ASSISTED LIPOTRANSFER IN THE CORRECTION OF AESTHETIC AND POST-TRAUMATIC DEFORMITIES OF FACIAL SOFT TISSUES.....219

TRAUMATOLOGY

31. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov Azim**
STUDYING THE RESULTS OF RECONSTRUCTIVE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF COMBINED MENISCLE WOUNDS.....228
32. **Axtamov Azim, Axtamov A'zam**
DIAGNOSIS AND MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF ACETABULUM INJURIES (LITERATURE REVIEW).....233
33. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov Azim**
EXPERIENCE IN TREATING INTRA-ARTICULAR FRACTURES OF THE DISTAL PART OF THE HUMERUS IN CHILDREN.....241
34. **Davirov Sharof Majidovich, Urinbaev Payzilla Urinbaevich, Mansurov Djalolidin Shamsidinovich**
OSTEOPLASTIC RECONSTRUCTION OF EXTENSIVE DIAPHYSEAL LONG BONE DEFECTS USING EXTERNAL FIXATION DEVICES.....246

PEDIATRICS

35. **Choliev Matyoqub Sulaymanovich, Khotamov Khusniddin Narzullayevich, Tilavov O'ktam Khamrayevich**
SOFT TISSUE NECROSIS IN CHILDREN: CLINICAL FEATURES, DIAGNOSIS AND PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT.....256
36. **Umarova Saodat Sulaymonovna**
VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY AS A PREDICTOR OF INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE RHEUMATIC FEVER.....264

37. **Rakhmatullaev Akmal Abadbekovich, Ergashev Mukhammadjon Tursunovich**
EFFECTIVENESS OF ENDOSCOPIC CORRECTION METHODS IN CHILDREN WITH
PRIMARY HIGH-GRADE VESICoureTERAL REFLUX.....275
38. **Akhmedzhanova Nargiza Ismailovna, Ganieva Marifat Shokirovna, Majidova Nilufar
Mansuralievna.** INNOVATIV METHODS OF EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF
TUBULOINTERSTISIAL LESIONS IN ACUTE PYELONEPHRITIS IN CHILD.....281
39. **Terebayev Bilim Aldamuratovich, Barnakulov Umrzok Khasanovich**
PROBLEMS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF DOLICHOSIGMA ASSOCIATED
WITH CHRONIC CONSTIPATION IN CHILDREN.....288
40. **Tilavov Uktam Khamraevich, Chuliev Matyokub Sulaimonovich, Khotamov Khusniddin
Narzullaevich, Abduqodirov Oybek Ahmadjonovich**
DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF CYSTIC ADENOMATOID MALFORMATION OF
THE LUNGS IN CHILDREN.....299
41. **Tukhtaev Firdavs Mukhitdinovich, Kadirov Jonibek Fayzullayevich**
PERSONALIZED METABOLIC APPROACHES IN CHILDREN'S MEDICAL
REHABILITATION.....307
42. **Ibragimova Sapura Zakhidovna, Almedova Nargiza Nigmatjonovna, Botirov Mirzokhid
Mansurzhon Ugli, Shadibekova Oksana Borisovna, Aripova Nazokat Bahodirovna,
Erimbetova Indira Oralbaevna**
RESULTS OF THE USE OF EMICIZUMAB IN PATIENTS WITH HEMOPHILIA A – A
PILOT SINGLE-CENTER STUDY.....312
43. **Khaidarov Khusan Anvarovich**
THE ROLE OF VITAMIN D STATE IN DETERMINING THE SEVERITY AND
EFFECTIVENESS OF INPATIENT TREATMENT OF RECURRENT RESPIRATORY
TRACT INFECTIONS IN YOUNG CHILDREN.....319

SURGERY

44. **Abdurahmonov Ma'mur Mustafaevich, Umedov Xushvaqt Alisherovich,**
ASSESSMENT OF THE IMMUNE SYSTEM STATUS IN ACUTE DESTRUCTIVE
PANCREATITIS.....325
45. **Kurbanov Aslbek Sadullaevich, Arziev Ismoil Alievich, Arzieva Gulnora Borievna**
DIAGNOSTIC AND THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF LAPAROSCOPY IN PATIENTS
WITH BLUNT ABDOMINAL TRAUMA.....331
46. **Yuldashov Parda Arzikulovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich, Sayinaev Farrukh
Karamatovich**
OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF POSTOPERATIVE VENTRAL
HERNIAS BASED ON LAPAROSCOPIC PROSTHETIC METHODS.....336
47. **Kurbanova Sanobar Yuldashevna, Kamalov Zainitdin Saifutdinovich, Azizova Zukhra
Shukhratovna**
CLINICAL, IMMUNOLOGICAL, AND IMMUNOGENETIC FEATURES OF DISEASE
DEVELOPMENT IN ADULT PATIENTS WITH PYELONEPHRITIS (A LITERATURE
REVIEW).....346
48. **Umedov Xushvaqt Alisherovich, Abdurahmonov Ma'mur Mustafaevich**
CONTEMPORARY CLINICO-MORPHOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF ACUTE
PANCREATITIS AND ITS COMPLICATIONS.....355
49. **Ollabergenov Odilbek Tozhiddinovich, Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich, Parpiev
Mirziyod Mirsaitovich**
CURRENT TRENDS IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF LIVER
ECHINOCOCCOSIS IN CHILDREN.....362

50. **Askarov Pulat Azadovich, Bazarov Bahrom Boymamatovich, Kurbaniyazov Zafar Babadjanovich**
THE IMPACT OF CONCOMITANT SURGICAL PATHOLOGY ON THE OUTCOMES OF SIMULTANEOUS OPERATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH VENTRAL HERNIAS AND MORBID OBESITY.....369
51. **Egamberdiev Abdukahhor Abduqodirovich, Arzieva Gulnora Borieva**
ASSESSMENT OF CLINICAL OUTCOMES AND TECHNICAL FEATURES OF ENDOVIDEOSURGICAL TREATMENT OF HIATAL HERNIA.....377
52. **Madazimov Madamin Muminovich, Turaev Feruz Fakhtullayevich, Kiziun Yana Viktorovna, Pustovetova Maria Gennadievna, Akramova Nozima Akramovna, Kiyamov Azizbek Utkirovich**
STUDY OF BREAST BLOOD SUPPLY USING DUPLEX ULTRASOUND IN REDUCTION MAMMOPLASTY.....385

INFECTIOUS DISEASE

53. **Imamov Otabek Sunnatovich, Mahmudov Sherzod Xasanovich, Djumaev Normurod Davlatovich, Bakhodirova Shahlo Bahoriddinovna, Tokhtayev Gairatillo Shukhratillo ugli.**
THE IMPORTANCE OF TEMPERATURE IN THE ETIOLOGY AND MODERN LABORATORY DIAGNOSTICS OF DERMATOMYCOSIS.....394
54. **Imamov Otabek Sunnatovich, Mahmudov Sherzod Xasanovich, Djumaev Normurod Davlatovich, Ernazarova Feruzabonu Ravshanbekovna, Tokhtayev Gairatillo Shukhratillo ugli**
MODERN ETIOLOGICAL SPECTRUM OF DERMATOMYCOSIS PATHOGENS IN THE TASHKENT REGION.....403
55. **Yusupov Mashrab Ismatillovich**
GUT MICROBIOTA: CORRELATION OF PHYSICAL LOAD, DIET, AND HEAT EXCHANGE.....409
56. **Faizullaev Sherzod Kobiljon ugli, Shakharov Dilshod Zhura ugli, Tukhtaev Shohzod Eshmurod ugli, Khuzhamberdiev Sodikjon Uchkun ugli, Samibaeva Umida Khurshidovna**
FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL PICTURE OF THE NEW CORONAVIRUS INFECTION (COVID-19).....420
57. **Samibaeva Umida Khurshidovna, Faizullaev Sherzod Kobiljon ugli, Shakharov Dilshod Zhura ugli, Tukhtaev Shohzod Eshmurod ugli, Khuzhamberdiev Sodikjon Uchkun ugli**
EVALUATION OF THE CLINICAL EFFICACY OF GLYCYRRHIZIC ACID IN PATIENTS WITH COVID-19.....435
58. **Samibaeva Umida Khurshidovna, Faizullaev Sherzod Kobiljon ugli, Shakharov Dilshod Zhura ugli, Tukhtaev Shohzod Eshmurod ugli, Khuzhamberdiev Sodikjon Uchkun ugli**
EVALUATION OF THE CLINICAL EFFICACY OF GLYCYRRHIZIC ACID IN PATIENTS WITH COVID-19.....447
59. **Rashidov Zafar Rakhmatullaevich**
CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF DOPLEROGRAPHY IN THE DETECTION AND MONITORING OF RENAL TUBERCULOSIS.....453

OPHTHALMOLOGY

60. **Nazirova Zulfiya Rustamovna, Turakulova Dilfuza Mukhitdinovna, Khamrayev Shakhruh Ilkhom ugli.**
SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CONGENITAL AND ACQUIRED CATARACTA IN CHILDREN: ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS AND STAGES.....460

61. **Turakulova Dilfuza Mukhitdinovna, Nazirova Zulfiya Rustamovna, Axrorova Malika Nosir qizi.**
ANALYSIS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF INTRAOCULAR LENS SUBLUCATION IN CHILDREN.....470
62. **Iskandarova Shakhnoza Tulkinovna, Miralimova Malika Mukhammadovna, Yangiyeva Nodira Rakhimovna**
ASSESSMENT OF THE INFORMATIVE VALUE OF PARENTAL QUESTIONNAIRES IN THE EARLY DETECTION OF REFRACTIVE DISORDERS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN.....477

NEUROSURGERY

63. **Asadov Khamidulla Fatkhullaevich, Okhunov Alisher Oripovich, Asadov Khumoyun Hamidullaevich.**
A NERVE-SPARING ENDOSCOPIC TUNNEL TECHNIQUE FOR THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CHRONIC OCCIPITAL MIGRAINE.....485
64. **Okhunov Alisher Oripovich, Asadov Khamidulla Fatkhullaevich, Asadov Khumoyun Hamidullaevich.**
STRATEGY FOR SELECTING THE EXTENT AND STAGING OF SURGICAL TREATMENT IN COMBINED FORMS OF CHRONIC MIGRAINE.....492

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STUDYING THE RESULTS OF RECONSTRUCTIVE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF COMBINED MENISCLE WOUNDS

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ABSTRACT

Our work is devoted to assessing the long-term results of treating patients after meniscus suturing in combination with arthroscopic surgery of the anterior cruciate ligament with the use of a popliteal flexor tendon graft. In our study, between 2024 and 2025, 93 patients underwent surgery to restore damaged menisci. Treatment results were analyzed by dividing into 2 groups depending on the treatment method. The main study group included 46 patients (27 women and 19 men), who underwent 51 meniscus restoration surgeries (27 medial and 24 lateral). Both menisci were restored in 5 patients. The control group included 47 patients (27 women and 20 men) who underwent anterior cruciate ligament plasty combined with meniscus resection (36 medial and 16 lateral). Patients in this group correspond to the main group in terms of gender, age, and time after surgery. When comparing the long-term treatment outcomes of two groups of patients with stitched and resected menisci during arthroscopic plasty of the anterior cruciate ligament, the long-term treatment outcomes in the group with stitched menisci were better than in the group with resected menisci.

Keywords: meniscus, cruciate ligament, osteoarthritis, wound, resection, meniscus sutures.

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ИЗУЧЕНИЕ РЕЗУЛЬТАТОВ РЕКОНСТРУКТИВНОГО ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ КОМБИНИРОВАННЫХ РАНЕНИЙ МЕНИСКОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Наша работа посвящена оценке отдаленных результатов лечения больных после ушивания менисков в сочетании с артроскопической пластикой передней крестообразной связки с

применением трансплантата их подколенного сгибательного сухожилия. В нашем исследовании в период с 2024 по 2025 год операции по восстановлению поврежденных менисков были проведены у 93 пациентов. Результаты лечения были проанализированы путем разделения на 2 группы в зависимости от метода лечения. В основную группу исследования вошли 46 больных (27 женщин и 19 мужчин), которым выполнены 51 операции по восстановлению менисков (27 медиальных и 24 латеральных). 5 больным произведено восстановление обоих менисков. В контрольную группу вошли 47 больных (27 женщин и 20 мужчин), которым выполнена пластика передней крестообразной связки в сочетании с резекцией мениска (36 медиальных и 16 латеральных). Пациенты этой группы соответствуют основной группе по полу, возрасту и времени после операции. При сравнении отдаленных результатов лечения двух групп больных с ушитыми и резецированными менисками при артроскопической пластике передней крестообразной связки отдаленные результаты лечения в группе с ушитыми менисками были лучше, чем в группе с резецированными менисками.

Ключевые слова: мениск, крестообразная связка, остеоартроз, рана, резекция, швы мениска.

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MENISKLARNING KOMBINATSIYALASHGAN JAROXATLARIDA QO'LLANILADIGAN REKONSTRUKTIV XIRURGIK DAVOLASH NATIJALARINI O'RGANISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Bizning ishimiz menisklarni tikishdan keyin bemorlarni davolashning uzoq muddatli natijalarini ularning tizza osti bukuvchi paylari transplantatini qo'llagan holda oldingi xojsimon boylam artroskopik plastikasi bilan birgalikda baholashga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqotimizni 2024-2025 yillar orasida jaroxatlangan menisklarni tiklash amaliyoti 93 bemorga o'tkazildi. Davolash usuliga kura 2 guruhga bo'lib davolash natijalari tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqotni asosiy guruhiga 46 bemor (27 ayol va 19 erkak) kiritildi, ularga 51 menisk tiklash amaliyoti (27 medial va 24 lateral menisk) bajarildi. 5 bemorga ikkala meniskni tiklash amalga oshirildi. Nazorat guruhiga 47 bemor (27 ayol va 20 erkak) kiritildi, ularga menisk rezeksiyasi (36 medial va 16 lateral menisk) bilan birga oldingi xojsimon boylam plastika qilish amalga oshirildi. Ushbu guruh bemorlari jins, yosh va operatsiyadan keyingi vaqt bo'yicha asosiy guruhga mos keladi. Old xojsimon boylam artroskopik plastikasida menisklar tikilgan va rezeksiya qilingan bemorlarning ikki guruhini davolashning uzoq muddatli natijalarini taqqoslaganda, menisklar tikilgan guruhda davolashning uzoq muddatli natijalari menisklar rezeksiya qilingan guruhga qaraganda yaxshiroq bo'ldi.

Kalit so'zlar: menisk, xojsimon boylam, osteoartroz, jaroxat, rezeksiya, menisk choklari.

Dolzarbli. Tizza bo'g'imi odamning tayanch-harakatlanish apparatining eng ko'p shikastlanadigan bo'g'imi bo'lib, barcha bo'g'imlar shikastlanishining 50% gacha va butun oyoq bilan bog'liq shikastlanishlarning 24% ni tashkil etadi [8]. Tizza bo'g'imi jarohatlariga faol hayot kechiradigan va sport bilan shug'ullanadigan odamlar moyil bo'ladi [2,7,8]. Menisklarning shikastlanishi tizza bo'g'imi sohasidagi og'riqning eng keng tarqalgan sababi bo'lib, yildan-yilga bunday shikastlanishlar soni ortib bormoqda.

Menisklarning shikastlanishi ko'pincha oldingi xojsimon boylam shikastlanishi bilan birga keladi (65% gacha) [1]. Ushbu shikastlanishlar ko'pincha faol hayot tarzini olib boradigan mehnatga layoqatli yoshdagi odamlarda uchraydi. Menisklar va oldingi xojsimon boylamning shikastlanishi jarohatdan keyingi uzoq muddatli davrda osteoartroz rivojlanish xavfini oshiradi, ularning qo'shma shikastlanishida esa xavf yanada yuqori bo'ladi [4,5]. Menisklardagi rekonstruktiv operatsiyalar

meniskni saqlab qolish imkonini beradi, bu osteoartroz rivojlanishini sekinlashtirishga yordam beradi, menisk transplantatsiyasi va tizza bo'g'imini endoprotezlashni kechiktirishga imkon beradi.

Jarrohlarning shikastlangan menisklarni davolash bo'yicha qarashlarini o'rganib chiqib, shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, XX-asrning o'rtalariga qadar ochiq meniskektomiya ko'pincha amalga oshirilgan, ya'ni meniskning ko'pini yoki barchasini olib tashlashgan. Ba'zi mualliflar menisklarni keraksiz deb olib tashlash mumkin bo'lgan rudement to'qima sifatida qarashgan [6].

Meniskni tiklash birinchi marta Annandale T. tomonidan ilmiy manbalarga keltirilgan (16-rasm) 1885 yilda, lekin o'sha paytda bu amaliyot keng tarqalmagan va keyingi 50 yil ichida yanada rivojlangan.

Yarim asr o'tgach, 1936 yilda King D. itlar ustida tadqiqot o'tkazdi va meniskni olib tashlaganidan keyin degenerativ o'zgarishlar paydo bo'lishini isbotladi. Shuningdek, u meniskning parakapsular zonasidagi yirtilishlar davolanish imkoniyatiga ega ekanligini ko'rsatdi [9].

Maqsad: Menisklar va old xojsimon boylamning birgalikdagi jaroxatlanishlarida davolash natijalarini yaxshilash va gonoartrozni profilaktikasidir.

Material va usullar. Respublika travmatologiya va ortopediya ilmiy amaliy tibbiyot markazining Samarqand filiali Yirik bo'g'imlar ortopediyasi bo'limida 2024-2025 yillar orasida jaroxatlangan menisklarni tiklash amaliyoti 93 bemorga o'tkazildi. 88 bemorda meniskni tikish oldingi xojsimon boylamni (m. Semitendinosus va m. Gracilis paylaridan) plastik jarrohlik bilan birgalikda amalga oshirildi, qolgan 5 bemorga meniskni o'zini tikish o'tkazildi. Davolash natijalari 2 guruhga bulib urganilgan asosiy va nazorat guruhlari.

Shu tarzda, asosiy guruhga 46 bemor (27 ayol va 19 erkak) kiritildi, ularga 51 menisk tiklash amaliyoti (27 medial va 24 lateral menisk) bajarildi. 5 bemorga ikkala meniskni tiklash amalga oshirildi.

Nazorat guruhiga 47 bemor (27 ayol va 20 erkak) kiritildi, ularga 2024-2025 yillar orasida menisk rezeksiyasi (36 medial va 11 lateral menisk) bilan birga oldingi xojsimon boylam plastika qilish amalga oshirildi. Ushbu guruh bemorlari jins, yosh va operatsiyadan keyingi vaqt bo'yicha asosiy guruhga mos keladi.

Davolash va natijalar. Bizning tadqiqotimiz menisklardagi rekonstruktiv operatsiyalarning uzoq muddatli natijalarini tizza osti bukuvchi mushaklari paylaridan autotransplantat yordamida OXB plastikasi bilan birgalikda kompleks tahlil qilishga qaratilgan.

Tadqiqotning asosini 2024-2025-yillarda RITOIATMSF klinikasi negizida OXB plastikasi bilan birgalikda menisklarni tikish amaliyoti bajarilgan 46 nafar (27 nafar ayol va 19 nafar erkak) bemorni jarrohlik davolashning uzoq muddatli natijalarini tahlil qilindi.

Nazorat guruhi sifatida 47 nafar (27 nafar ayol va 20 nafar erkak) bemor tanlab olindi, ularga menisklar rezeksiyasi xuddi shu vaqt oralig'ida OXB plastikasi bilan birgalikda amalga oshirildi.

Barcha bemorlar operatsiyadan oldingi bosqichda, operatsiyadan keyingi erta davrda, shuningdek, keyingi nazorat tekshiruvlarida sinchkovlik bilan tekshirildi. Tizza bo'g'imining standart tekshiruvi o'tkazildi, shu jumladan ko'rik, palpatsiya, harakatlar hajmini aniqlash va boylamlar va menisklarning shikastlanishiga xos testlar o'tkazildi. Operatsiyadan keyingi davrda operatsiyadan keyingi chandiqlar, ularning rangi, shakli, shuningdek, harakatchanligiga e'tibor qaratildi.

Meniskning bitishini baholash uchun biz Henning S.E. va hammualliflar tomonidan taklif etilgan tasnifdan foydalandik. Operatsiyadan oldin va keyin bajarilgan tizza bo'g'imining MRTsi asosida meniskning bitish darajasi taqqoslandi.

Henning S.E. va hammualliflar tomonidan taklif etilgan tasnif bo'yicha operatsiyadan oldingi va keyingi MRTni baholashda bemorlarning 84% (21) da to'liq sog'ayish, 12% (3) da qisman, 4% (1) da to'liq bo'lmagan sog'ayish aniqlandi. Menisklar to'liq va qisman bitmagan bemorlarda oxirgi nazorat ko'rigi paytida operatsiya qilingan tizza bo'g'imi sohasida hech qanday klinik alomatlar, shuningdek, og'riq va noqulaylik hissi aniqlanmadi.

So'nggi nazorat ko'rigida nazorat guruhidagi barcha bemorlarga savollar berildi, ularning javoblari bajarilgan operatsiyadan qoniqishini baholash uchun ishlatildi. Bundan tashqari, ulardan, agar operatsiyaning natijasini oldindan bilganingizda, ushbu operatsiyaga rozi bo'larmidingiz, deb so'rashgan. 100% (46) holatda bemorlar u yoki bu darajada operatsiya natijasidan qoniqish hosil

qilishgan. "Yo'q" degan javob bo'lmadi. 96% (44) bemorlar, agar uning natijasini oldindan bilganlarida, ushbu operatsiyaga rozi bo'lishardi.

Nazorat guruhidagi bemorlarning uzoq muddatli natijalar tahlil qilinganda, mediana Cincinnati shkalasi bo'yicha 93 ballni tashkil etdi. A'lo natijalar 93% (42) bemorlarda, qoniqarli natijalar 7% (3) bemorlarda olindi. Yaxshi va qoniqarsiz natijalar bo'lmadi.

Mediana Lysholm shkalasi bo'yicha uzoq muddatli natijalar tahlil qilinganda 90 ballni tashkil etdi. Bemorlarning 69% (31) da a'lo natijalar, 22% (10) da yaxshi, 9% (4) da qoniqarli natijalar olindi. Qoniqarsiz natijalar bo'lmadi.

Bemorlarning asosiy guruhi jaroxatlarning asosiy qismi meniskning orqa qismlarida, ya'ni meniskning orqa shoxi sohasida joylashgan. Barcha jaroxatlar bo'ylama parakapsulyar yoki bo'ylama xarakterga ega bo'lgan.

Uzoq muddatli natijalar tahlil qilinganda, mediana Cincinnati shkalasi bo'yicha 97 ballni tashkil etdi (kvartillararo diapazon 90 dan 100 ballgacha). A'lo natijalar 93% (42) bemorlarda, qoniqarli natijalar 7% (3) bemorlarda olindi. Yaxshi va qoniqarsiz natijalar bo'lmadi.

Mediana Lysholm shkalasi bo'yicha uzoq muddatli natijalar tahlil qilinganda 95 ballni tashkil etdi. Bemorlarning 69% (31) da a'lo natijalar, 22% (10) da yaxshi, 9% (4) da qoniqarli natijalar olindi. Qoniqarsiz natijalar bo'lmadi.

Bemorlarning 93% (43) odatiy jismoniy faollikka qaytdi. So'nggi tekshiruv paytida uchta bemorda operatsiya qilingan tizza bo'g'imida 20⁰ bukilish cheklanishi saqlanib qoldi, ammo bu cheklanish ularga kundalik hayotda va sport bilan shug'ullanishda hech qanday xalaqit bermadi.

Barcha mavjud ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilganda, oldingi xochsimon bog'larning artroskopik plastikasida menisklarni tizza osti bukuvchi mushaklari paylaridan tayyorlangan autotransplantat bilan tikish jarrohlik amaliyotidan keyingi uzoq davrda samarali jarrohlik aralashuvi bo'lib, menisklar rezeksiyasini bajarishga nisbatan yaxshiroq natijalarni ko'rsatadi degan xulosaga kelish mumkin.

Meniskda rekonstruktiv operatsiyalardan so'ng operatsiyadan oldingi va keyingi MRT oldingi xojsimon boylam plastikasi bilan birgalikda har doim ham klinik ko'rinish bilan bog'liq emas. MRT ma'lumotlariga ko'ra meniskning qisman va to'liq bitmasligi (Henning mezoni bo'yicha) saqlanib qolayotgan uzilishning ishonchli belgisi hisoblanmaydi va klinik ko'rinishlarga ega bo'lmashligi mumkin.

Xulosa.

1. Oldingi xochsimon bog'larning artroskopik plastikasida menisklarni tizza osti bukuvchi mushaklari paylaridan olingan autotransplantat bilan tikish o'rtacha 6±1,8-yil (1-yildan 8-yilgacha) kuzatuv davrida samarali jarrohlik aralashuvi hisoblanadi.

2. Old xochsimon boylam artroskopik plastikasida menisklar tikilgan va rezeksiya qilingan bemorlarning ikki guruhini davolashning uzoq muddatli natijalarini taqqoslaganda, menisklar tikilgan guruhda ortopedik shkalalar (Cincinnati, Lysholm) bo'yicha baholashda davolashning uzoq muddatli natijalari menisklar rezeksiya qilingan guruhga qaraganda yaxshiroq bo'ldi.

3. Menisklardagi rekonstruktiv operatsiyalardan keyingi magnit-rezonans tomografiya ma'lumotlari har doim ham klinik ko'rinish bilan bog'liq emas. MRT ma'lumotlariga ko'ra meniskning qisman va to'liq bitmasligi (Henning mezoni bo'yicha) saqlanib qolayotgan uzilishning ishonchli belgisi hisoblanmaydi va klinik ko'rinishlarga ega bo'lmashligi mumkin.

4. "Hammasi ichida" texnikasi bo'yicha menisklarni tikish uchun ko'rsatmalar bo'lib, qon bilan ta'minlangan sohada jaroxat lokalizatsiyasida menisklarning orqa shoxi va tanasi sohasidagi bo'ylama, parakapsulyar, pastki va yuqori to'liq bo'lmagan beqaror jaroxatlar hisoblanadi.

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